

PRODUCTION OF A STEADY CONDUCTANCE AS A DETERMINANT OF THE JOSHI-EFFECT UNDER SILENT DISCHARGE

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Ageing by exposure to discharge stabilises the discharge current, increasing markedly the *Joshi-effect* Δi , over a wide range of potentials and using different detectors. The above result and that the high frequency part of the current is the chief seat of Δi , agree with *Joshi's* theory of the phenomenon. The vacuo-junction is better adapted for Δi detection than a more current-sensitive rectifier.

The time-variation of the discharge current i , produced by a constant potential kV , applied to an isolated sample of pure chlorine in a sealed ozonizer and especially, of the magnitude of the above phenomenon viz., a reversible and instantaneous current decrease, Δi on irradiation was observed under X-rays by *Joshi* (*Curr. Sci.*, 1944, 13, 278), and under visible light by *Deo* (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1945, A21, 76), the latter over long periods of discharge. In a recent theory of this effect *Joshi* (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1946, Part III, p. 25) has postulated that an adsorption-like layer is formed on the electrodes derived, in part, from the gas, activated under the discharge, which plays an important part in the production of Δi . The results of the following work, carried out primarily to study the influence of ageing, are in accord with this conception.

EXPERIMENTAL

The general procedure was essentially similar to that of *Deo* (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1943 A19, 117). Fig. 1 shows the apparatus used: A Siemens' type ozonizer (1) filled with purified chlorine was activated at the required potential kV and

FIG 1.

50 cycles frequency. The discharge current, i was measured with a Cambridge vacuo-junction (V. J. in Fig. 1) connected to a sensitive mirror galvanometer by connecting L. T. with (1). Despite constancy of the applied potential, during time

periods *immediately* after its application, i was observed to be markedly unstable; no values for the characteristic i could therefore be obtained. The current, i was rendered comparatively stable on introducing a 3000 ohm Dubilier resistance between L, T. the low tension electrode of the ozonizer and the detector viz., vacuo-junction (Fig 1). The values for i (in dark) recorded after every 5 seconds for one series of observations at 10.7 kV, given in Table I, illustrate the position. That an exposure to discharge for 2 hours stabilises conduction is also shown in Table I by the values of i (in dark) at the above potential and made in precisely the same manner as mentioned earlier.

TABLE I

Influence of ageing on the discharge current (ozonizer 1).

Before ageing	4.4	5.2	4.5	5.4	4.8	5.2	5.5	5.8
	5.3	5.0	5.7	5.8	5.7	5.8	5.4	
After ageing	7.1	7.1	7.1	7.2	7.2	7.1	7.3	7.1
	7.1	7.1	7.0	7.2	7.3	7.4	7.3	

As a sensibly constant current i , characteristic of the applied potential kV, was observed, the effect of irradiating the ozonizer was studied. This was directed transversely to the ozonizer-axis, using a 200-watt incandescent (glass) bulb. When an opaque shutter (Fig. 1) between this and the ozonizer was raised, so as to let the light fall on the latter, i showed the Joshi-effect, viz., an instantaneous photo-diminution Δi , restorable to i_{dark} on shutting off the light. Several series of observations were taken for this effect Δi at various kV, and after different durations of exposure to the discharge. Table II is a typical group of results. The relative Joshi-effect % Δi is given by $\frac{\Delta i}{i_{\text{dark}}} \times 100$.

TABLE II

Influence of applied potential on Joshi-effect (Δi) under steady conductance after ageing (ozonizer 1).

Applied potential. kV.	i_{dark} .	i_{light} .	Δi .	% Δi .
9.1	4.9	4.7	0.2	4.1
9.6	5.9	5.4	0.5	8.5
10.2	6.7	6.0	0.7	10.5
10.7	7.5	6.7	0.8	10.7
11.2	8.2	7.3	0.9	11.0
11.8	9.0	7.8	1.2	13.3

A series of observations was next made with ozonizer (2), excited in the range 2 to 8 kV. The discharge current i was measured with a vacuo-junction (as in the previous series with ozonizer 1); and also separately with a metal oxide type rectifier, connecting L, T. with (2) in Fig. 1. The current and the Joshi-effect Δi and % Δi were also measured using a moderate size aerial (Fig. 1), kept at a fixed distance near the ozonizer (Joshi, *Nature*, 1944, 154, 147). The aerial currents were observed separately with the vacuo-junction and with the oxide type rectifier, introduced respectively between H. F. and (1); and between H. F. and (2), in Fig. 1. These measurements with the aerial denote the high frequency part of the discharge current which has been shown to be the chief seat of this effect (Joshi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 67).

Using ozonizer (2) ageing under discharge was produced at various durations. Table III summarises one typical set of results, using both the detectors mentioned above. The quantities Δi , and $\% \Delta i$ observed at a series of kV and at a constant period of ageing are shown in the same vertical column; the above quantities, observed after ageing, are shown within brackets below those, before ageing.

TABLE III
Variation of current (i) and Joshi-effect (Δi) after different durations of ageing under the discharge (ozonizer 2)

(Quantities observed after 'ageing' are shown within brackets).

Ageing (in hrs.)	2				2				5			
	i_{dark}	i_{light}	Δi	$\% \Delta i$	i_{dark}	i_{light}	Δi	$\% \Delta i$	i_{dark}	i_{light}	Δi	$\% \Delta i$
(a) A. C. Detector used—vacuo-junction.												
5.9	1.98 (1.95)	1.67 (1.61)	0.31 (0.34)	15.7 (17.4)	1.82 (1.99)	1.52 (1.55)	0.30 (0.43)	16.5 (21.7)	1.90 (1.79)	1.48 (1.15)	0.42 (0.61)	22.1 (34.1)
6.1	2.92 (2.55)	2.51 (2.35)	0.41 (0.50)	14.0 (17.8)	2.57 (2.53)	2.24 (4.11)	0.33 (0.62)	12.8 (20.5)	2.05 (2.81)	2.47 (1.52)	0.58 (0.99)	19.0 (35.2)
6.4	4.20 (4.12)	3.74 (3.45)	0.46 (0.67)	11.0 (10.3)	3.94 (4.30)	3.49 (3.55)	0.45 (0.74)	11.4 (17.2)	4.09 (4.11)	3.42 (2.74)	0.67 (1.37)	16.4 (33.3)
6.7	5.47 (5.27)	4.89 (4.54)	0.58 (0.73)	10.9 (13.9)	5.40 (5.59)	4.97 (4.72)	0.43 (0.87)	8.0 (15.5)	5.53 (5.37)	4.73 (3.77)	0.80 (1.80)	14.5 (29.5)
6.9	6.68 (6.72)	6.02 (5.77)	0.66 (0.95)	9.9 (14.1)	6.50 (6.75)	5.59 (5.75)	0.91 (0.98)	9.4 (14.5)	6.80 (6.75)	5.74 (4.90)	1.06 (1.85)	15.8 (27.4)
7.2	7.98 (8.07)	7.28 (6.95)	0.70 (1.12)	8.8 (13.9)	7.90 (8.08)	7.18 (6.99)	0.82 (1.09)	7.9 (12.5)	8.09 (8.34)	6.91 (6.26)	1.18 (1.98)	14.6 (23.7)
(b) A. C. Detector used—oxide rectifier.												
2.7	3.9 (3.3)	3.9 (3.3)	— —	— —	3.8 (3.5)	3.8 (3.5)	— —	— —	3.7 (3.4)	3.7 (3.4)	— —	— —
4.0	9.8 (8.6)	9.6 (8.4)	0.2 (0.2)	2.0 (2.3)	9.2 (9.3)	9.0 (9.0)	0.2 (0.3)	2.2 (3.2)	9.5 (9.0)	9.2 (8.7)	0.3 (0.3)	3.2 (3.3)
5.3	21.0 (17.9)	20.4 (17.3)	0.6 (0.5)	2.9 (2.5)	19.5 (19.1)	18.6 (18.3)	0.9 (0.8)	4.8 (4.2)	19.4 (18.3)	18.5 (17.4)	0.9 (0.9)	4.6 (4.9)
5.8	26.8 (22.0)	25.1 (20.5)	1.5 (1.5)	5.6 (6.8)	24.5 (25.2)	23.3 (23.9)	1.2 (1.3)	4.9 (5.2)	25.3 (24.1)	23.3 (21.9)	2.0 (2.2)	7.9 (9.1)
5.9	33.5 (33.5)	37.1 (30.5)	1.5 (3.0)	3.9 (8.9)	37.5 (36.7)	34.5 (32.7)	3.0 (1.0)	8.0 (10.9)	38.3 (35.1)	33.9 (28.8)	4.5 (6.3)	11.8 (17.9)
6.1	54.6 (56.0)	51.1 (53.0)	3.5 (4.0)	5.4 (7.1)	57.5 (61.2)	53.5 (54.9)	4.0 (8.3)	8.9 (10.3)	62.8 (56.1)	55.8 (43.1)	7.0 (13.0)	11.1 (23.2)

D I S C U S S I O N

The results given in Table I show that as an effect of 2 hours' ageing under the discharge, i_{dark} is increased sensibly to a constant maximum. Tables I and II show that i , variable in the range 4.4 to 5.8 (in arbitrary units) was produced at 10.7 kV before ageing and at 9.2 kV afterwards. A series of observations of i at 5 seconds intervals, before and after ageing as in Table I, shows, however, that its

effect is to stabilise i , and not necessarily to increase it. This is seen from the results with ozonizer (2) in Table III, for different durations of ageing excited in the range 2 to 8 kV and using two detectors. Such an almost permanent alteration of i under the large applied fields employed, cannot be ascribed to changes in the ionic mobility, and / or ionic cluster formation (Deo, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1945, A21, 76). Also, no ordinary type of chemical reaction leading to a current change (Joshi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1939, 8, 548) is possible within an elementary gas like chlorine. This alteration in the conductivity suggests the production of a strained or an unstable surface condition of the electrodes under the influence of the operating fields (Joshi, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part III, p. 51) due, in part, to interaction between the wall material and the activated gas under discharge leading to surface products of a limited life. It is significant to observe that if the discharge was discontinued for say 48 hours, and re-started at the original potential, i was again found to be unstable and was steadied only after ageing *i.e.*, after a further continued exposure to discharge. Similar results were observed in bromine vapour (Joshi, *loc. cit.*).

The results in Tables I to III also show that i , rendered steady by ageing, is an optimum condition for the production of the Joshi-effect, at any rate in chlorine at a given applied potential. Using ozonizer (1) the results in Table II show that whilst both Δi and $\% \Delta i$ increase, the latter changes appreciably slowly (Joshi, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1945, A22, 389) as kV is increased. For ozonizer (2) using a vacuo-junction, the net Joshi-effect, Δi increases with the applied potential varied from 5.9 to 7.2 kV, whereas the corresponding $\% \Delta i$ decreases (Joshi, *loc. cit.*). There is a marked influence of ageing both on Δi and $\% \Delta i$. The increase of Δi with kV during ageing is more rapid; the corresponding decrease of $\% \Delta i$, however, is less marked. Under similar conditions of excitation (Table III) when the oxide rectifier is used, considering relatively in a given series, Δi and $\% \Delta i$ before and after ageing increase first slowly, and then rapidly as the potential is increased from 2.7 to 6.1 kV.

The oxide rectifier is more current sensitive than the vacuo-junction. It was remarkable to observe, however, that whilst the former recorded i at voltages too small for the vacuo-junction, no Joshi-effect could be observed therewith. At 6.1 kV (Table III) i , both in dark and in light recorded by the rectifier, is apparently much greater than that observed with the vacuo-junction. It is interesting to note, however, that $\% \Delta i$, as observed with the vacuo-junction, is sensibly greater than that with the oxide rectifier. Such a selective behaviour of the oxide rectifier was also observed earlier by Joshi (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, p. 51; *Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 67).

Results for the Joshi-effect are significant when i in the aerial is observed. For these measurements, the oxide rectifier and a more current sensitive vacuo-junction than that in Tables I-III, were used. Both recorded a comparable aerial current, which represented the high frequency part of i and the chief seat of Δi (Joshi *Curr. Sci.* 1945, 14, 67). The latter showed about 30% Joshi-effect; that with the former was negligibly small. This difference in the behaviour of the two detectors is strikingly similar to that observed in the L. T. circuit of the ozonizer (Table III), in which the H. F. is the minor component. This may be attributed to the circumstance that the vacuo-junction has a more uniform characteristic than the oxide rectifier (Joshi, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1945, A22, 225), and is subject to the limitations of its rectifying mechanism.

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